

Original Research

Effects of graded inclusion of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal on growth and feed utilisation in *Clarias gariepinus*

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Abstract

The Nigerian aquaculture industry, despite its 50-year existence and vast cultivable water resources, still struggles to meet domestic fish demand, largely due to high feed costs. This study investigated the growth performance and physicochemical responses of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed graded levels (0%, 5%, 10%, and 20%) of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM). Standard methodologies were used to assess the physicochemical qualities and growth parameters such as weight, length, specific and daily growth rates, and feed conversion ratio and condition factor. The results revealed that the proximate composition of JTLM had moderate nutritional values: 25.5% crude protein, 5.0% fibre, 20.3% fat, 9.5% ash, 0.9% moisture, and 38.8% nitrogen-free extract. Water quality parameters remained within optimal ranges, with slight reductions in dissolved oxygen and increases in BOD, TSS, and conductivity at higher inclusion levels (20%). Growth performance was significantly improved in the 5% and 10% JTLM groups, which exhibited superior weight gain, daily growth rate, specific growth rate (SGR), and feed conversion ratio (FCR) compared to the control and 20% treatments. The best FCR (3.52–4.18) was also observed at these levels. Although all groups maintained healthy condition factors (>1.0), the 20% JTLM group had the lowest survival rate. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) across treatments. The findings indicate that JTLM is a viable, cost-effective feed ingredient for African catfish when used at appropriate inclusion levels. It is recommended to limit JTLM inclusion to 5–15%, combine it with high-protein ingredients, and further explore its effects on other cultured fish species.

Keywords

physicochemical parameters, growth performance, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, plant-based protein

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Vpliv postopnega dodajanja moke iz listov *Jatropha tanjorensis* na rast in izkoristek krme pri *Clarias gariepinus*

Izvleček

Nigerijska ribogojna industrija kljub 50-letni tradiciji in obsežnim vodnim virom, primernim za gojenje rib, še vedno težko zadovoljuje domače povpraševanje po ribah, predvsem zaradi visokih stroškov krme. V tej študiji smo preučevali rastne zmogljivosti in fizikalno-kemijske odzive mladice ribe *Clarias gariepinus*, ki so bile krmiljene z različnimi deleži (0 %, 5 %, 10 % in 20 %) listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Za oceno fizikalno-kemijskih lastnosti in parametrov rasti, kot so teža, dolžina, specifične in dnevne stopnje rasti ter razmerje pretvorbe krme in kondicijski faktor, so bile uporabljene standardne metodologije. Rezultati so pokazali, da je imela sestava JTLM zmerne hranilne vrednosti: 25,5 % surovih beljakovin, 5,0 % vlaknin, 20,3 % maščob, 9,5 % pepela, 0,9 % vlage in 38,8 % ekstrakta brez dušika. Parametri kakovosti vode so ostali v optimalnih mejah, z rahlim zmanjšanjem raztopljenega kisika in povečanjem BOD, TSS in prevodnosti pri višjih vključitvenih ravneh (20 %). Rastna zmogljivost se je znatno izboljšala v skupinah z 5 % in 10 % JTLM, ki so pokazale boljše telesno maso, dnevno stopnjo rasti, specifično stopnjo rasti (SGR) in razmerje pretvorbe krme (FCR) v primerjavi s kontrolno skupino in obdelavami z 20 %. Najboljši FCR (3,52–4,18) je bil prav tako opazen pri teh vsebnostih. Čeprav so vse skupine ohranile zdrave kondicijske faktorje (>1,0), je imela skupina z 20 % JTLM najnižjo stopnjo preživetja. Statistična analiza je potrdila statistično značilne razlike ($p \leq 0,05$) med poskusi. Rezultati kažejo, da je JTLM uporabna in stroškovno učinkovita sestavina krme za afriškega soma, če se uporablja v ustreznih vsebnostih. Priporoča se, da se vsebnost JTLM omeji na 5–15 %, da se ga kombinira s sestavinami z visoko vsebnostjo beljakovin in da se nadalje raziskujejo njegovi učinki na druge gojene ribje vrste.

Ključne besede

fizikalno-kemijski parametri, rastni kazalniki, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, rastlinske beljakovine

Introduction

The Nigerian aquaculture industry is over five decades old (Olagunju *et al.*, 2007); however, domestic fish production has remained inadequate to meet the protein needs of the rapidly growing population. Despite this challenge, Nigeria possesses enormous aquaculture potential. Ita *et al.* (1985) reported that the country has over 13 million hectares of cultivable water bodies suitable for aquaculture development. In addition, several cultivable fish species, both exotic and indigenous, have been documented (Ngueku, 2015), indicating strong prospects for expanding fish production.

Fish is one of the most nutritious and highly demanded sources of animal protein worldwide. The increasing human population has further intensified the demand for fish and fishery products. However, the sustainability of aquaculture is largely dependent on the availability of quality and affordable feeds. CMFRI and SAARC (2013) identified fish feed as one of the major constraints to aquaculture development,

contributing significantly to the decline of the agricultural sector. The success of fish production depends heavily on feed quality and cost (Udo and Umanah, 2017).

The major ingredients used in aquafeeds include fish-meal, soybean meal, and maize. Unfortunately, these conventional feedstuffs are expensive and increasingly scarce due to competition for human food, livestock feed, and industrial uses (Rahman *et al.*, 2023). In Nigeria, the cost of fish feed has risen drastically over the years. Daily Trust (2016) reported an 80–100% increase in feed prices within eight years, forcing many fish farmers, particularly in Lagos State, out of business. Similarly, Okon *et al.* (2020) reported that a bag of Blue Crown feed sold for about ₦10,500, but the same brand now costs over ₦24,400, representing about a 138% increase (Thompson *et al.*, 2024). These rising costs reduce farmers' profit margins and threaten the sustainability of aquaculture.

To address this challenge, alternative, cost-effective, and sustainable feed resources must be explored. Plant-based proteins are considered the most suitable substi-

tutes for fishmeal in freshwater diet formulation (Naylor *et al.*, 2009). The inclusion of plant protein ingredients in fish diets has increased due to their relatively low cost and balanced amino acid profiles (Mahboob, 2014). Consequently, attention has shifted toward underutilised plant resources as potential ingredients for aquafeeds.

One such promising plant resource is the genus *Jatropha*. In Nigeria, *Jatropha tanjorensis* is commonly known as “Hospital Too Far,” “Catholic vegetable,” “Iyana-Ipaja,” or “Lapalapa” (Iwalewa *et al.*, 2005). *Jatropha* plantations can yield up to four tons of seeds per hectare annually, producing about one ton of protein-rich kernel meal (Makkar and Becker, 1997). This indicates the potential of *Jatropha* seed meal as a sustainable protein source for aquaculture feeds.

However, the utilisation of *Jatropha* seed meal has been limited by the presence of toxic and anti-nutritional factors. Its toxicity is mainly attributed to phorbol esters, along with other antinutrients such as trypsin inhibitors, lectins, phytates, saponins, tannins, and alkaloids (Makkar and Becker, 2009; Pelletier *et al.*, 2015). These compounds may restrict their use in animal feeding. Nevertheless, studies have shown that appropriate processing methods, such as heat treatment and solvent extraction, can significantly reduce phorbol esters and eliminate most antinutrients, thereby improving the safety and nutritional quality of *Jatropha* meals (Goel *et al.*, 2007).

Although research on *Jatropha* species has focused mainly on their distribution, cultivation, and nursery development, studies on *Jatropha tanjorensis* as a feed ingredient remain limited (Sudheer *et al.*, 2009). Available evidence, however, supports its potential as a protein source in aquaculture. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of *Jatropha* seed meal in the diets of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Kumar *et al.*, 2008), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Kumar *et al.*, 2009), Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Abozaid *et al.*, 2016), and African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2016; Musa *et al.*, 2018).

In Nigeria, the most commonly cultured fish species include catfish and tilapia. Among them, the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is the most popular due to its fast growth, hardiness, tolerance to low dissolved oxygen, and ability to survive under high stocking densities (Adikwu, 2003). It is highly valued for its high protein content, palatability, and adaptability to various Nigerian culinary styles, making it an important contributor to household nutrition and food security (Ezenwa, 2006).

To meet FAO’s recommended fish consumption rate of 12.5 kg per capita annually, Nigeria requires about 1.5 million metric tonnes of fish per year (FAO, 2017). However, current production remains insufficient, and demand continues to rise. This underscores the need to explore alternative feed ingredients that are affordable, sustainable, and capable of supporting both fish growth and nutritional quality.

Therefore, this study is designed to provide nutritionists, aquafeed manufacturers, and fish farmers with a practical, economical, and sustainable alternative for feed formulation. Specifically, the study evaluates the effect of *Clarias gariepinus* growth fed graded levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* meal. The findings also contributed to the baseline information for improving feed utilisation, reducing production costs, and enhancing profitability and sustainability within the Nigerian aquaculture industry.

Materials and Methodology

Experimental Location

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, University of Uyo. The feeding trial was conducted under semi-controlled outdoor conditions. The experiment was carried out in eight (8) black, round rubber plastic tanks with a working volume of 50 L each, placed on an open field to allow exposure to natural sunlight and ambient environmental conditions. The tanks were made of high-density plastic material and operated as static water systems with periodic water renewal. This study was conducted between April and June 2025, which corresponds to the early rainy season in southern Nigeria. During this period, ambient temperature ranged between approximately 26–32 °C, with relative humidity of 70–85% and a natural photoperiod of about 12 h light and 12 h dark. Water temperature followed ambient conditions and was monitored regularly to ensure suitability for *Clarias gariepinus* culture.

The tanks were cleaned regularly, and uneaten feed and faecal materials were siphoned to maintain water quality. Water was partially renewed every two weeks to prevent the accumulation of metabolic wastes. All husbandry practices were carried out uniformly across treatments to minimise environmental variation and ensure reliable assessment of dietary effects.

Collection and Identification

Fresh branches of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf were obtained from a farm in Uyo L.G.A, Akwa Ibom State. The leaves and stems of the plant were plucked and taken to the Herbarium of the Department of Botany and Ecological Studies, University of Uyo, for proper identification.

Collection, Identification and Processing of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM)

Fresh, mature leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* were collected from healthy, non-contaminated stands within cultivated home gardens in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. At harvest, the plants were free from visible disease symptoms and insect damage. Both leaves and small portions of the stem were initially collected for proper taxonomic identification; however, only the leaves were used for feed preparation, while the stems served solely for authentication purposes.

The plant material was authenticated by the Laboratory Technologist, Department of Botany, University of Uyo, Nigeria, and a voucher specimen was deposited for reference. After harvest, the leaves were rinsed with clean water to remove surface debris and soaked in water for 30 h to reduce anti-nutritional factors, unlike the method of Adejoro *et al.* (2013), who soaked for 24 h. The soaked leaves were drained and oven-dried at 55 °C for 72 h (three days) until a constant weight and crispy texture were achieved, after which they were milled into powder using a mechanical milling machine and sieved through a 2-mm mesh to remove coarse fibre, yielding fine *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM).

Preparation of Experimental Diets Containing JTLM

Other feed ingredients, including soybean seeds, maize meal, fish meal, cassava flour, and vitamin–mineral premix, were purchased from a reputable commercial feed store in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Soybean seeds were toasted according to the methods described by Tiamiyu *et al.* (2015) and Okomoda *et al.* (2020) to reduce anti-nutritional factors, while the remaining ingredients were used as purchased.

All ingredients were weighed according to the formulated diet compositions and thoroughly mixed to obtain a homogeneous blend. The appropriate proportions of JTLM

were incorporated into the basal diet to replace part of the conventional protein source as required for each treatment. The mixed diets were pelleted, air-dried, and stored in airtight containers until use for the feeding trial.

Diet formulation and preparation

The powdered meal produced was mixed directly with the basal diet. It was added to the diets at concentrations of 0%, 5%, 10% and 20% of feed labelled Control, JTLM 1, JTLM 2 and JTLM 3, respectively (Table 1). Compounded feeds were pelletized (2mm) using the pelletizing machine, sundried, allowed to cool in the open air, packed and stored in an opaque nylon bag.

Warm water was added to the premixed ingredients and homogenised until a dough-like paste was formed. The dough was then passed through a pelleting machine. The moist pellets were sundried to a constant weight and were kept in air-tight containers prior to the experiment. The percentage composition of the experimental diets is given in Table 1.

Experimental design and feeding

A total of 160 apparently healthy *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings with an average initial weight of 4.54 ± 0.47 g were purchased from Fish Feed Solution Cooperative, No. 5 Osuk Ntan, off Ikot Akpanobong, Ibiono Ibom, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The fish were transported to the experimental facility and acclimatised for 7 days in holding tanks, during which they were fed a control diet and observed for health and activity.

After acclimatisation, fish were randomly assigned to four dietary treatments in duplicate, giving a total of 8 experimental tanks. Each tarpaulin tank (100 × 50 cm) was stocked with 20 fingerlings, resulting in a total of 160 fish and a uniform stocking density across treatments. Randomisation was done by assigning fish sequentially to tanks after gentle mixing to avoid size bias.

Each tank was filled with 15,000 mL (15 L) of unchlorinated water. Manual aeration was provided by gently stirring the water in each tank at regular intervals (morning, afternoon, and evening) to enhance oxygen diffusion and prevent stratification. In addition, uneaten feed and faeces were siphoned daily to maintain water quality. Water was partially exchanged (75% twice weekly) throughout the experimental period.

Table 1. Composition of the experimental diets (g kg⁻¹ feed).

Tabela 1. Sestava poskusnih krmnih mešaníc (g/kg krme).

Ingredients	Experimental diets			
	Control	JTLM 1 (5%)	JTLM 2 (10%)	JTLM 3 (20%)
JTM	0	5	10	20
Fish meal	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00
Maize	32.60	27.60	22.60	12.60
Soybeans	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
Wheat meal	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00
Salt	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Vitamin premix	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Fish oil	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
Total	100	100	100	100

Note: C (0%) – 0 % inclusion of JTLM; JTLM 1 - 5%; JTLM 2 - 10%; JTLM 3 - 20%

The fish were fed experimental diets containing graded levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) for 10 weeks (70 days). Feeding was done twice daily at 07:00 h and 17:00 h at a rate of 5% of body weight (Kassaye, 2012). On sampling days, fish were fed three hours after weighing to reduce handling stress.

Fish in each tank were batch-weighed weekly, and the feeding ration was adjusted accordingly to reflect 5% of the updated biomass. Mortalities, if any, were recorded immediately and removed from the tanks, and the number of fish per tank was noted for accurate calculation of growth and feed utilisation indices.

Throughout the experiment, tanks were kept under similar environmental conditions to minimise variation among treatments, ensuring that any observed differences could be attributed to the dietary treatments.

The study was conducted in accordance with all applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals. The research did not involve the killing of any of the fish samples. Additionally, the number of fish used (160 samples) did not exceed the threshold requiring ethical approval (200 samples and above) as per the local regulations. The study was performed on a private fish farm licensed by the State Government, which lies outside the jurisdiction of the Ethical Approval Research Committee in Nigeria. For these reasons, no formal ethical approval number was issued for this study.

Analysis of physicochemical parameters

The physicochemical parameters of the culture water were monitored weekly throughout the 10-week experimental period. Parameters measured included pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity, total suspended solids (TSS), and biological oxygen demand (BOD₅). Water samples were collected from each experimental tank in the morning between 08:00 and 09:00 h, prior to feeding, to minimise diurnal variation and ensure consistency in sampling conditions. All instruments were calibrated before each sampling event in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions to ensure accuracy and reliability of measurements. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 10.0. The dissolved oxygen meter was calibrated using the air-saturation method, while the conductivity meter was calibrated using a standard potassium chloride (KCl) solution. Thermometers were verified against a reference thermometer before use.

Water pH was measured using a digital mini pH meter (Model 55, Fisher Scientific, Denver, CO, USA). Water temperature was determined using a mercury-in-glass thermometer (0–100 °C range), which was immersed in the water sample for approximately 5 minutes to attain thermal equilibrium before recording.

Dissolved oxygen was measured in situ using a YSI Model 58 dissolved oxygen meter (Yellow Springs

Instrument Co., OH, USA). Electrical conductivity was determined using an electrolytic conductivity meter and expressed in $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$.

Total suspended solids (TSS) were determined using the gravimetric method. A known volume (100 mL) of water sample was filtered through a pre-weighed glass-fibre filter paper. The filter paper was dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 hours, cooled in a desiccator, and re-weighed. TSS was calculated as the difference in weight of the filter paper before and after filtration, divided by the volume of the sample filtered and expressed in mg L^{-1} .

Biological oxygen demand (BOD_5) was determined using the 5-day incubation method. Water samples were transferred into 300-mL BOD bottles, with appropriate dilution using oxygen-saturated distilled water where necessary. Initial dissolved oxygen (DO_1) was measured immediately after sample preparation. The bottles were incubated at 20 ± 1 °C for 5 days in the dark to prevent photosynthesis. After incubation, the final dissolved oxygen (DO_5) was measured. BOD_5 was calculated as the difference between DO_1 and DO_5 , taking dilution factors into account. Nitrification inhibition was applied where necessary following standard procedures.

All analyses were conducted in accordance with the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater as described by APHA (1998).

Fish Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation

Growth performance and nutrient utilisation parameters were evaluated using standard formulae described by Dabrowski (1986), Jauncey (2008), Jamabo and Alfred-

Ockya (2008), and Pangni *et al.* (2008).

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from the experiment were subjected to a One-Way Analysis of Variance using the IBM-SPSS statistical package version 22. Means of parameters were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test with an acceptable value of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

Proximate Composition of the Soaked and oven-dried *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM)

Table 2 reveals that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) used in this study contained 25.5% crude protein as the highest and moisture level (0.9%) as the lowest in concentration.

Physicochemical Parameters of Water

The average values across the 10-week period are presented in Table 3. The DO decreased with increasing JTLM inclusion. DO in the 20% JTLM group (4.8 mg L^{-1}) was significantly lower than the control (5.3 mg L^{-1}). Conductivity increased significantly from $430 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (0%) to $470 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (20%). The TSS increased significantly in the 10% and 20% JTLM groups. BOD progressively increased with higher JTLM inclusion. The 20% group (2.6 mg L^{-1}) had significantly higher BOD than the control (1.8 mg L^{-1}).

Tabela 2. Proximate Composition of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM). Expressed as mean \pm SD.

Table 2. Sestava listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Izraženo kot povprečje \pm SD.

Nutrient Component	Percentage (%)
Crude Protein	25.5
Crude Fibre	5.0
Crude Fat (Ether Extract)	20.3
Ash	9.5
Moisture	0.9
Nitrogen-Free Extract (NFE)	38.8

Tabela 3. Water Quality Parameters. Expressed as mean \pm SD.Table 3. Parametri kakovosti vode. Izraženo kot povprečje \pm SD.

Parameter	0% JTLM	5% JTLM	10% JTLM	20% JTLM	Optimal Range (FME, 2006)
pH	6.7 \pm 0.10 ^a	6.8 \pm 0.11 ^a	6.9 \pm 0.12 ^a	7.0 \pm 0.09 ^a	6.5–8.5
Temperature (°C)	27.4 \pm 0.4 ^a	27.5 \pm 0.3 ^a	27.6 \pm 0.5 ^a	27.5 \pm 0.4 ^a	25–30
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	5.3 \pm 0.2 ^a	5.1 \pm 0.2 ^b	5.0 \pm 0.2 ^b	4.8 \pm 0.2 ^c	\geq 5.0
Conductivity (μ S cm ⁻¹)	430 \pm 12 ^a	440 \pm 15 ^b	460 \pm 14 ^b	470 \pm 16 ^b	< 500
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	12.0 \pm 2.1 ^a	13.5 \pm 2.4 ^{ab}	14.2 \pm 2.5 ^b	15.0 \pm 2.6 ^b	< 50
BOD (mg L ⁻¹)	1.8 \pm 0.3 ^a	2.0 \pm 0.2 ^a	2.3 \pm 0.3 ^b	2.6 \pm 0.4 ^c	< 10

Note: Values with different superscripts across rows are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. JTLM = *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal; DO = Dissolved Oxygen; TSS = Total Suspended Solids; BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand.

Tabela 4. Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation of *Clarias gariepinus* Fed Different Levels of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf Meal (JTLM). Expressed as mean \pm SD.Table 4. Rast in izkoristek krme pri ribi *Clarias gariepinus*, krmljeni z različnimi količinami listne moke *Jatropha tanjorensis* (JTLM). Podatki so izraženi kot povprečje \pm SD.

Parameter	0% JTLM	5% JTLM	10% JTLM	20% JTLM
Initial Mean Weight (g)	4.62 \pm 0.34	4.85 \pm 0.51	4.58 \pm 0.49	4.12 \pm 0.52
Final Mean Weight (g)	12.00 \pm 0.48 ^a	14.00 \pm 0.42 ^b	13.70 \pm 0.46 ^b	10.00 \pm 0.39 ^c
Weight Gain (g)	7.39 \pm 0.28 ^a	9.22 \pm 0.31 ^b	9.13 \pm 0.33 ^b	5.95 \pm 0.26 ^c
Initial Total Length (cm)	6.17 \pm 0.51	7.77 \pm 0.39	7.85 \pm 0.41	6.64 \pm 0.31
Final Total Length (cm)	8.90 \pm 0.42 ^a	10.50 \pm 0.39 ^b	10.77 \pm 0.43 ^b	9.10 \pm 0.37 ^a
Initial Standard Length (cm)	4.71 \pm 0.36	4.91 \pm 0.45	6.43 \pm 0.31	4.21 \pm 0.26
Final Standard Length (cm)	6.55 \pm 0.35 ^a	7.12 \pm 0.34 ^b	8.20 \pm 0.38 ^c	6.12 \pm 0.32 ^a
Daily Growth Rate (g day ⁻¹)	0.106 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.132 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.130 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.085 \pm 0.01 ^c
Specific Growth Rate (% g day ⁻¹)	1.36 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.52 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.56 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.28 \pm 0.04 ^c
Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)	3.94 \pm 0.02 ^b	3.58 \pm 0.05 ^a	3.52 \pm 0.06 ^a	4.18 \pm 0.07 ^c
Condition Factor (K)	1.70 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.22 \pm 0.03 ^c	1.10 \pm 0.03 ^c	1.33 \pm 0.03 ^b
Initial Number of Fish	40	40	40	40
Final Number of Fish	35	33	37	30
Survival Rate (%)	87.5	82.5	92.5	75.0

Note: Superscripts (a, b, c) within rows indicate statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$). Values with the same letter are not significantly different, while those with different letters are significantly different.

Figure 1. Showing some growth parameters.

Slika 1. Prikaz nekaterih parametrov rasti.

Growth Performance and Feed Utilisation of *Clarias gariepinus* Fingerlings

The growth performance indices of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed diets containing 0%, 5%, 10%, and 20% JTLM for 10 weeks are shown in Table 4.2. Each group started with distinct average initial weights and length parameters. Fish fed 5% and 10% JTLM diets exhibited significantly higher final weights and weight gains ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the control (0%) and 20% groups. The daily growth rate recorded was the highest in the 5% (0.132 ± 0.01 % g day⁻¹) JTLM group, followed closely by 10% (0.130 ± 0.01) JTLM group. While the specific growth rate was recorded as the highest in 10% (1.56 ± 0.03 % g day⁻¹) in the JTLM group, followed closely by 5% (1.52 ± 0.03 % g day⁻¹). Best (lowest) FCR was recorded in the 5% and 10% groups (3.58 ± 0.05 and 3.52 ± 0.06), which were statistically superior to both the 0% (3.94) and 20% (4.18) inclusion levels.

The highest K was observed in the control group (1.70). However, fish in all groups maintained a healthy range (>1.0). The survival rate was high across treatments (75.0% to 92.5%), but 20% JTLM (75%) had a significantly lower survival rate than the others. Statistical analysis (ANOVA)

showed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in weight gain, DGR, SGR, FCR, PI and K among treatments. Figure 1 is a graphical representation of some growth parameters in this study. Here, the fish fed diets containing 5% and 10% JTLM showed significantly higher final mean weight, total length, and standard length compared with the control (0%) and 20% JTLM groups. The 10% JTLM treatment produced the highest overall growth performance. In contrast, fish fed 20% JTLM recorded the lowest growth values, indicating reduced growth at higher inclusion levels. Initial weight and length were similar across all treatments.

Discussion

The proximate composition of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal (JTLM) indicates that it is a moderately protein-rich plant ingredient with potential value as a supplementary feed component in aquaculture diets. The crude protein content (25.5%) obtained in this study is comparable to values reported by Obikaonu *et al.* (2012) and Asuquo and Ifon (2021), although lower than the 35–45% dietary protein requirement of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings (FAO, 2017).

Kumar *et al.* (2008) reported higher crude protein values (35.3–35.6%) for processed and raw JTLM, while Ugboqu *et al.* (2014) reported 29.4% for *Jatropha curcas* seeds. Although the protein level in JTLM is below the optimal requirement for sole use, it remains nutritionally relevant when incorporated with conventional protein sources such as fishmeal and soybean meal (Asuquo and Ifon, 2021). Protein remains the most critical and expensive dietary component in fish production (Essien *et al.*, 2024); therefore, identifying cost-effective plant-based supplements without compromising fish health is of considerable importance.

The fibre (5.0%) and carbohydrate (NFE 38.8%) fractions suggest that JTLM may influence nutrient utilisation depending on inclusion level. High fibre content can impair digestibility and feed conversion in carnivorous fish such as *C. gariepinus*, which have limited capacity to digest complex plant polysaccharides (Olukunle, 2013). At moderate inclusion (5–10%), fibre may support gut motility without adversely affecting nutrient absorption. However, excessive fibre at 20% inclusion likely exceeded the digestive tolerance threshold, contributing to reduced feed utilisation efficiency.

The crude fat content (20.3%) indicates the presence of beneficial lipids essential for energy metabolism and physiological functions (NRC, 2011). This moderate lipid level likely supported an adequate energy supply without excessive fat deposition. Additionally, *Jatropha tanjorensis* contains phytochemicals such as flavonoids and saponins (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2015), which may contribute antioxidative and antimicrobial benefits, potentially enhancing fish health.

The ash content (9.5%) reflects the mineral composition and is within acceptable ranges for plant-based feed ingredients (NRC, 2011). Moisture content (9.8%) was below the 12% threshold associated with microbial spoilage (Al-Thobaiti *et al.* 2018), suggesting adequate processing and storage conditions.

The present study demonstrates that dietary inclusion of JTLM at moderate levels (5–10%) enhances growth performance and feed utilisation in *C. gariepinus* fingerlings, whereas higher inclusion (20%) results in reduced performance. Fish fed 5% and 10% JTLM showed significantly higher weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR), and improved feed conversion ratio (FCR) compared with the control and 20% groups ($p < 0.05$). The 10% inclusion level produced the most consistent growth response. These findings align with reports by Fagbenro *et al.* (2010), Al-Thobaiti *et al.* (2018), and Asuquo and Ifon (2021), who

observed improved performance at moderate plant-protein inclusion levels. Similarly, Adene *et al.* (2022) reported optimal performance of *C. gariepinus* at 10% inclusion of *Jatropha curcas* meal.

This pattern suggests that JTLM exerts a dose-dependent effect on growth, with beneficial outcomes at moderate inclusion and diminishing returns at excessive levels. However, the mechanisms underlying these responses cannot be definitively established from the present data. While reduced growth at higher inclusion levels may be associated with increased fibre content, altered nutrient balance, or anti-nutritional factors such as saponins and tannins (Musa *et al.*, 2018; Jimoh *et al.*, 2020), digestibility, palatability, toxicity, and metabolic responses were not directly measured. Consequently, these explanations remain plausible hypotheses rather than confirmed causal mechanisms.

Feed conversion efficiency was significantly improved at 5–10% inclusion and deteriorated at 20%, suggesting that excessive plant material may limit nutrient utilisation capacity in *C. gariepinus*. Although survival remained relatively high across treatments, slight reductions at 20% inclusion may reflect cumulative anti-nutritional effects, consistent with findings by Musa *et al.* (2018) and Jimoh *et al.* (2020).

Water quality parameters remained within acceptable limits for freshwater fish culture (APHA, 1998; Anyanwu *et al.*, 2012; Okon *et al.*, 2020). Temperature (27–28°C), pH (6.7–7.0), and dissolved oxygen ($\geq 4.8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were within optimal ranges, and no significant differences were observed among treatments ($p > 0.05$). Slight increases in BOD and TSS at higher JTLM inclusion levels were likely attributable to increased organic load from undigested plant material, as similarly observed by Amosu *et al.* (2023). However, these changes did not exceed critical thresholds and were unlikely to have constrained growth.

Several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged. Digestibility, palatability, and toxicity assessments were not conducted, limiting mechanistic interpretation. Haematological and biochemical indices were not evaluated, restricting assessment of physiological stress or metabolic alterations. The experimental duration was relatively short, and no cost-benefit analysis was performed to assess economic feasibility. Recognition of these limitations is essential for accurate interpretation and to guide future research.

Despite these constraints, the findings provide clear

evidence that JTLM can be incorporated into the diets of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings at moderate levels without compromising growth. The consistent pattern of enhanced growth and feed efficiency at 10% inclusion, coupled with reduced performance at 20%, indicates that JTLM functions effectively as a supplementary ingredient within a narrow optimal inclusion range rather than as a high-level replacement for conventional protein sources. Biologically, the results suggest that *C. gariepinus* can utilise JTLM-derived nutrients efficiently at moderate levels, but excessive inclusion may exceed the species' capacity to process plant-based components. Under the conditions of this study, a 10% inclusion level is therefore statistically and biologically justified.

Conclusion

The results revealed that diets containing 5% and 10% JTLM significantly improved growth parameters, including weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR) and feed conversion ratio (FCR), compared to the control (0%) and the 20% JTLM group. The 10% JTLM group recorded the best overall performance, indicating an optimal balance of protein supplementation and digestibility. Water quality parameters such as pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen remained within acceptable ranges across treatments, although BOD, TSS, and conductivity showed a slight increase at 20% inclusion. This suggests a threshold above which increased plant material may begin to compromise water quality and fish health. Furthermore, fish survival and condition factor remained high across all treatments, but a notable decline in survival rate at the 20% inclusion level indicates the possible impact of anti-nutritional factors and high fibre content at excessive JTLM incorporation. The proximate composition of JTLM, especially its moderate protein (22.5%), fat (4.3%), and carbohydrate level, supports JTLM as a potential cost-effective, plant-based ingredient in sustainable aquaculture feed formulation when properly included.

Recommendations

Based on this and similar studies, it is recommended that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf meal be included at 5% to 10% of total feed composition for *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings to achieve optimal growth and feed efficiency without compromising water quality or fish health. Also,

- JTLM should be well-dried, crushed, or fermented to reduce anti-nutritional factors such as tannins, saponins, and phytic acid, thereby improving nutrient availability and palatability.

To enhance JTLM-based diets, it is recommended to supplement with higher-protein sources like fishmeal, soybean meal, or amino acid concentrates to meet the nutritional requirements of catfish, especially during early growth stages.

- Further studies should be conducted to examine the long-term effects of JTLM inclusion on their proximate analysis, biochemical and haematological profiles, and JTLM should be used in other aquaculture species such as tilapia or *Heterobranchus spp.* for broader application.
- Future research integrating digestibility trials, physiological assessments, long-term feeding experiments, and economic evaluations will be necessary to fully define the nutritional and commercial potential of JTLM in aquaculture feeds.

Author's Contribution

Conceptualization, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.P.U.; methodology, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U., P.O.I., B.O.B., E.N.D. and B.O.E.; software, E.A.E.; validation, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; formal analysis, E.A.E.; investigation, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.P.U.; resources, E.A.E., A.O.O., P.O.I., B.O.B., E.N.D. and B.O.E.; data curation, E.A.E., A.O.O. and E.N.D.; writing—original draft preparation, E.A.E.; writing—review and editing, E.A.E., A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; supervision, A.O.O., E.P.U. and E.N.D.; funding acquisition, E.A.E., P.O.I., B.O.B. and B.O.E. All authors read and approved the final manuscript

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Data Availability

The research data is deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19056885>).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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